
**Geological Mapping for the Land Deformation Using Small UAV,
DInSAR Analysis and Field Observation at The Siak Bridge I and
II, Pekanbaru City, Indonesia**

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Abstract

Pekanbaru is the capital city of Riau province, located in the center of the Sumatra Island Indonesia is experiencing rapid economic progress. The city is split by Siak river. Big bridges that connect this city are Siak I Bridge and Siak II Bridge. The Quality of Siak bridges paid attention seriously in this previous time, especially for Siak I bridge deflection, despite completely built from past time. Also for Siak II Bridge it needs more attention incase of this bridge is the road for the heavy truck way. Geological mapping using a small UAV conducted to determine the deformation points on the site of Siak I bridge and Siak II Bridge areas, the study of Siak I Bridge and Siak II Bridge are also supported by the DInSAR analysis using ALOS PALSAR data of Pekanbaru city and Deflection observation that occurs in Siak I bridge and Siak II Bridge was measured during field observation. Results of small UAV 3D models analysis shows no negative land deformation on the Siak I Bridge and Siak II Bridge areas. DInSAR analysis shows the number of positive deformation of Siak I Bridge is 81 cm and Siak II Bridge is 48 cm. Deflection on Siak I Bridge was detected around 10-15 cm.

Keywords

Keywords: Pekanbaru city; Siak Bridges; Small UAV; DInSAR; Deflection

1. Introduction

Pekanbaru city (Figure 1) is the capital city of Riau province, Indonesia located 101°14' - 101°34' E and 0°25' - 0°45' N with sea level average from 5 - 50 meters. The northern part of this city is a plain area with average height 5 - 11 meter. The total area of Pekanbaru city is 632.26 km². Pekanbaru city is the one of the main city in Indonesia with the population of 1.2 million people based on Center for Indonesia Statistic Board, Pekanbaru branch released on 2014. The economical in Pekanbaru growth above 10% in a year, this number is above of Indonesia's economy growth which has 4.79% (Center for

Indonesia Statistic Board, 2014). This rapid growth needs infrastructure facilities to support people activities, meanwhile, Pekanbaru city is the strategic city located at the center of Sumatera Island. With this position, Pekanbaru city is the connector of the north-south littoral at the Sumatera Island, also as the connector between east and west of this island.

This importance of Pekanbaru city requires supporting infrastructures inevitably. One them is bridge facility. Pekanbaru city was split into two because it passed the great river named Siak River, the river is recognized as well as the deepest river in Indonesia. Siak River divides Pekanbaru city located at the Senapelan sub-district, Rumbai sub-district, and Rumbai Pesisir sub-district.

The establishment of the bridge as the community liaison activities in Pekanbaru, provide enormous positive impact by making the groove Pekanbaru ground transportation becomes easier, but the construction of this bridge also pose a risk to their land-use change and the condition of the bridge due to the pressure exerted by the bridge and traffic activities that are in it. This study aims to determine the effect given or experienced by land due to the construction of the bridge.

The bridge is located on the Siak River area of Pekanbaru city. Siak I bridge located at $0^{\circ}32'27.68''$ N and $101^{\circ}26'13.65''$ E, was built in 1973 and available to use in 1977 with the length 355 meter. Siak II bridge located at $0^{\circ}33'4.41''$ N and $101^{\circ}24'1.89''$ E, was built in 1990 with length 190 meters.

Figure 1. Map of Pekanbaru city, Riau Province, Indonesia.

2. Data and Method

Three methodologies were used for this research. Field mapping on Siak I, Siak II bridges were used small UAV with specifications: built-in camera with FOV (Field of View) 94° 20 mm (35 mm format equivalent) f/2.8 lens, 1/2.3" sensor and effective pixels: 12 M connected to the built-in GPS. Pictures were taking among 2 weeks for the whole bridges, starting from 20 May 2016 until 3 June 2016. The pictures were rendered using some software to produce a 3D model of mapping area.

Land-site deformation measurement of the bridge stand was measured using differential interferometry measurement with ALOS PALSAR level 1.1 data, the date from 25 May 2007 and 20 April 2011.

To analyze the differential interferometry on the ALOS PALSAR Level 1.1 data, the software used to process it, then choose the baseline (B) by looking the highest number and it should be in the first process. This baseline influenced by topography. Influences of topography (h) in interferograms given by:

$$\phi_{topo} = -\frac{4\pi.B^2}{\lambda.R_1.\sin\theta_0} \quad (1)$$

After selecting the data, coregistration process will generate (figure 2) accurate determination of phase differences, coregistration produces the master and slave data which ready for coregistration to combine of those data. Coregistration data is ready for interferogram generation with a flattened condition and the result for calculating the complex correlation coefficient between two acquisitions or coherence for generating topographic phase correction. By reducing interferogram phase and topographic phase correction will generate the differential interferogram.

$$Differential_{Interferogram} = phase_{ifg} - phase_{topo} \quad (2)$$

Generating the topographic phase correction will be available to produce the phase filtering. We used 2 types of Goldstein filtering with 0.5 x 0.5 and 0.3 x 0.3 coherence threshold. The data is ready to be unwrapped after finishing phase filtering process.

The compile between wrapped phase and unwrapped phase data will produce vertical displacement map which given by calculation as below:

$$vertical_{displacement} = \frac{\phi_{unwrapped}.\lambda}{-4\pi.\cos\theta_i} \quad (3)$$

Where LOS-to-Vertical factor or incidence angle from satellite data.

Vertical displacement map will generate the vertical displacement map reference, as the reference to combining with pixel from the point we chosen by substitute equation 2 to the equation below:

$$vertical_{displacement_reference} = (vertical_{displacement} + pixel_{value}) \quad (4)$$

Calculation of masking area with low coherence is to combine with the vertical displacement reference to get the result of interferometry. The calculation of masking area is given by:

$$ver_{disp_ref_mask} = IF (Coherence\ value) \geq (Scale\ value\ in\ meter) THEN\ 1\ ELSE\ NaN \quad (5)$$

Masking of vertical displacement reference is resulting file for Geocoding and projection map that used WGS84 with SRTM 3sec digital elevation model and nearest neighbour resampling method in Range-Doppler terrain correction.

Figure 2. Flowchart of inteferometric co-registration.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Area monitoring using small UAV

Mapping using a small UAV for Siak I bridge (Figure 3) and Siak II bridge (Figure 4) were used to produce a 3D result of the study area, using an overlapping technique to get the pictures of the study area, rendering software was used. The result from a 3D model of small UAV shows the land area of the bridge sites for Siak I, Siak II and residential area. The result showed no significant changes to the land especially for the land subsidence and land deformation. This analysis also supported by ALOS PALSAR differential interferometry analysis data in Pekanbaru city.

Figure 3. Location of Siak Bridges taken by Small UAV for Siak Bridge I.

3.2. Differential Interferometry Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR) analysis

Land deformation mapping on the site of Siak I, Siak II bridges shows the number that impacted in Pekanbaru city and around Siak bridges based on data analysis of ALOS PALSAR on 25 May 2007 and 20 April 2011. ALOS PALSAR Data Processing for these

scenes produces a differential interferogram (Figure 5) which was used further for processing to obtain the number of land deformation in this study area.

Figure 4. Location of Siak Bridges taken by Small UAV for Siak Bridge II.

Figure 5. Location of Siak Bridges taken by Small UAV for Siak Bridge II.

Based on DInSAR analysis, Pekanbaru city has the lowest deformation value of -540.36 mm in several southern and western area. For the highest deformation value is 1,274.50 mm in the eastern part of Pekanbaru city (Figure 6). DInSAR analysis was used 4 types scale which are 0.01, 0.1, 0.5 and 0.6. DInSAR analysis also shows there was no land subsidence in Pekanbaru city in the range of 2007-2011. This analysis also shows the topography information of Pekanbaru city which are the east area has the higher topography than south and west areas.

Differential interferometry analysis on the Siak I bridge and Siak II bridge (Figure 7) show the deformation in these areas are positive. Siak I bridge has 81 cm deformation value. For Siak II bridge has 48 cm deformation value and this site is the lowest value compare to another site of Siak bridges. DInSAR analysis for Siak I bridge and Siak II bridge did not detect any significant negative land deformation. This result gives mean, for the site of all Siak bridges was not impacted the bridge to fail.

Figure 6. Differential Interferometry Image for Pekanbaru city.

Figure 7. Differential Interferometry Image for Pekanbaru city.

3.3. Field observation for bridge deflection

Field observation show for the Siak Bridge I and II, there is no negative subsidence. For the land as the site of Siak Bridges stand; it still stable without no subsidence occurs detected.

4. Recommendation and Future Work

Periodical mapping using UAV needs to do in the future for at least 6 months to get the change of land-site by the time. The bridges need periodical maintenance,

especially for the Siak Bridge I and II, because these bridges have reached more than 20 years age.

5. Conclusion

The result of the study conducted on Siak bridges in Pekanbaru city is expected to provide input for Pekanbaru city government in preparing for the construction and preservation of existing bridges. The result of the mapping using small UAV's shows no area has decreased significantly in all regions around the site of Siak bridges land, UAV's mapping result is also supported by the analysis of land deformation using DInSAR analysis for ALOS PALSAR Data of Pekanbaru city that certifies the absence of negative surround Siak I bridge and Siak II bridge, Another supporting analysis is direct observation at Siak bridges. From the observation, big deflection did not find on the Siak I bridge and Siak II bridge. For further research, we will conduct another UAV mapping in the future and analyze the change detection for these bridges compare with current data.

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Reference

- Beiqi Shi, Chun Liu. 2015. UAV for Landslide Mapping and Deformation Analysis. International Conference on Intelligent Earth Observing and Applications 2015, edited by Guoqing Zhou, Chuanli Kang, Proc. of SPIE Vol. 9808, 98080P-1. doi: 10.1117/12.2207411.
- Center for Indonesia Statistic Board, 2014. <https://pekanbarukota.bps.go.id/Subjek/view/id/12#subjekViewTab3|accordion-daftar-subjek1>
- Chia-Sheng Hsieh, Mong-Han Huang, Tian-Yuan Shih, Jacques Angelier, Jyr-Ching Hu, Hsin Tung. 2011. Using differential SAR interferometry to map land subsidence: a case study in the Pingtung Plain of SW Taiwan. Nat Hazards. DOI 10.1007/s11069-011-9734-7
- Husnul Kausarian, 2015. Rock Mass, Geotechnical and Rock Type Identification Using SASW and MASW Methods at Kajang Rock Quarry, Semenyih, Selangor Darul Ehsan. Journal of Ocean, Mechanical and Aerospace -Science and Engineering-. Vol. 26. <http://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/ALOS/en/about/palsar.htm>
- Roni Ardiansyah, 2011. <https://ronymedia.wordpress.com/2011/12/08/perlukah-diragukan-kekuatan-jembatan-siak-iii/>
- Shi Hongyun, Yang Songlin, Liu Guang. 2011. The Application of InSAR in the Deformation Monitoring for Road Engineering - A Case Study: Dujiangyan, China. Fourth International Conference on Intelligent Computation Technology and Automation.